

NOVEL PROCESSING FOR DEPOSITION OF Cu NANOPARTICLES ONTO CARBON – APPLICATION TO ADAPTATIVE Cu-C COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Heat dissipation in power electronic systems is becoming a critical point due to increasing power of the chips. Copper is commonly used as material for heat sinks but the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of Cu is too high that affects the reliability of devices. Reinforcing Cu with carbon fibers or diamond, which combine high thermal conductivity and low CTE is potentially a good solution. The optimization of the composite properties is mainly related to the control of C/Cu interfaces knowing these two elements do not chemically react together. A new process consisting in covering C fibers or D by Cu nanoparticles has been investigated. It allows the formation of a chemical bond between C and Cu and is supposed to enhance the thermal and thermomechanical properties of the densified Cu/CF and Cu/D composites. These properties will be compared with those of the same composites fabricated by a conventional process of powder metallurgy. Furthermore the evolution of the physical properties under thermal cycling will be measured and compared to the results obtained with classical Cu/CF or Cu/D composites.

2 Starting materials

Dendritic copper powder ($k = 400 \text{ W/m.K}$, $\text{CTE} = 17 \text{ ppm/K}$) from Eeka Granules Poudmet is used as matrix. Short high modulus carbon fibers ($k// = 140\text{-}900 \text{ W/m.K}$, $\text{CTE}// = -1 \text{ ppm/K}$) from Mitsubishi Chemical and synthetic diamond ($k \approx 1500 \text{ W/m.K}$, $\text{CTE} \approx 0 \text{ ppm/K}$) from Henan Zhongxin Industry were used as reinforcements. The functionalizing agent is an ester phosphate named CP213 or a solution of orthophosphoric acid. The solvent is ethanol.

3 Coating of C reinforcements

Two ways of deposition were explored. The first is based on the functionalization of the carbon (fibers or diamond particles) in a solution of orthophosphoric acid heated at 80°C during 30 minutes. After rinsing, filtering and drying the C, the treated reinforcement is mixed with dendritic copper powder and annealed under air at 400°C during 2 hours. A final heat treatment under Ar/H_2 (5 vol. %) during 1 hour leads to the formation of spherical submicronic particles on the functionalized substrate.

The other method involves an ester phosphate as functionalizing agent which is mixed with the carbon, dendritic copper powder and the solvent in a 3D mixer during 4 hours. This functionalization step is followed by an annealing treatment of the mixture under air at 400°C during 2 hours and deoxidization at 400°C during 1 hour under Ar/H_2 (5 vol. %). For both surface treatments the final compound consists in the carbon-based substrate fully covered with spherical submicronic Cu particles whose density or size are linked with the experimental procedure.

4 Microstructural characterizations

Figure 1 shows the microstructure of CuO-CF powder after annealing treatment under air. A particular nanowire shape of the CuO grains can be observed [1,2]. Figure 2-a and 2-b show respectively the homogeneous copper coating on C fibers and diamond after heat treatment under Ar/H_2 . The size of Cu spheres does not exceed one micron and depends on the quantity of phosphorus on C surface, the deoxidization treatment duration and temperature. The following mechanism is proposed to explain the formation of the Cu nanoparticles: under Ar/H_2 atmosphere the CuO nanowires sublime and when the vapor pressure is saturated Cu

condenses on the reactive sites of the functionalized substrate. The size and shape of the deposited particles depend on the experimental parameters. For example if the amount of phosphorus bonded at the substrate's surface is high, there are a lot of nuclei per unit surface and they can coalesce to form micrometric Cu particles. On the contrary, if a few P is fixed at the surface of the substrate the number of nuclei per unit surface is low and these nuclei are too far from each other to coalesce during annealing and the Cu grains remain in the nanometric range. In any case if the time of annealing is long enough a mechanism of Ostwald ripening leads to a grain growth.

The final morphology of the deposited particles is almost spherical as it is the most stable shape from a thermodynamic point of view. Observations at higher magnification of the Cu grains show polyhedral shapes with several facets. This kind of morphology reminds the equilibrium shapes described by Wulff [3] where surfaces presenting the lowest free surface energy are favoured during the growth of crystalline particles.

5 Cu-CF and Cu-D composites

The Cu coated CF and diamond are densified by hot uniaxial pressing at 650°C, 50 MPa, during 20 minutes under vacuum to avoid oxidation of the Cu matrix. The relative density is systematically measured as it has a strong influence on thermal properties. Thermal diffusivity is measured by laser flash method with a LFA457 and CTE measured by dilatometry on a DIL402C, both from Netzsch group. The properties of Cu-D composites are isotropic but those of Cu-CF are anisotropic because of an orientation of the fibers in a plane perpendicular to the direction of compaction.

Dilatometry measurements both on Cu-D and Cu-CF composite materials do not show any modification of CTE induced by our process.

On the contrary, it was shown an increase of 50 % in thermal diffusivity of Cu-30 vol. % diamond composites elaborated by the deposition technique compared to the same composites issued from powder metallurgy (simple mechanical mixing followed by sintering). The Cu particles chemically linked to diamond allow a strong bonding with the

copper matrix that enhances heat transfer within the composite.

The thermal properties of Cu-FC composites elaborated by the deposition method are similar to that obtained by a classical powder metallurgy technique due to the averaging effect caused by the orientation of the fiber during hot pressing.

Thermal cycling is in progress to highlight a potential increase of the composites lifetime fabricated by our technique. Indeed, we assume that the chemical bond created between reinforcement and matrix will maintain initial thermal properties during more than 1000 cycles (-45°C, +150°C under air) that would be better than the evolutions measured for powder metallurgy composites.

6 Coating of other substrates

The same Cu nanoparticles coating can be obtained on various non-carbonated substrates like alumina, silicon carbide, silicon, polyimide. Figure 3 shows copper nanoparticles selectively deposited on a silicon wafer. In fact, this new method of coating allows a deposition of Cu nanoparticles only on the functionalized parts of the substrate. Here (fig. 3), the functionalization solution was dropped along a line on a silicon substrate (leading to the presence of phosphor atoms bonded to the surface). After the reduction step, the wafer was covered by Cu particles strictly following the line where the functionalization occurred.

7 Conclusions

Thanks to the new deposition process, thermal properties of copper-diamond composites were significantly enhanced. A study of the evolution of thermal properties during thermal cycling is in progress. Indeed we expect a better reliability of the composites fabricated with our technique than that of composites processed by powder metallurgy.

This process could also solve many problems of assembling for example in power electronic devices. Actually thanks to this technique it would be possible to remove solder joints by reporting directly metallic parts on ceramic parts covered by Cu particles. The process can also be applied for the deposition of other metals like Mn, Ti, Ni that would extend the field of applications.

Fig.1. SEM micrograph of CuO-CF powder

Fig.2. SEM micrograph of a) Cu-CF; b) Cu-D composites powders

Fig.3. SEM micrograph of Cu nanoparticles selectively deposited on a Si wafer

References

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